

Report on Rating Open Science Projects

Team MAJIG - Maria, Abhay, Joelma, Inès, Guillaume

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Objective: Our task was to rate all the open science projects given to us here, according to Vienna Principles(1).

Data Description: The given data(2) consists of 7 Open Science projects - namely, Human Brain Project(3), Even Horizon Telescope(4), Science Feedback(5), Open Worm(6), Safecast(7), Sensebox(8) and Kiron(9). The columns of this Google sheet(2) represent the criteria described in the Vienna principles, based on which the ratings are made.

Procedure: First, we rated the Human Brain Project(3) together so as to get acquainted with the task at hand. Further, we split the task amongst all our team members from Team MAJIG and every member has rated 1 or 2 projects according to the Vienna Principles(1). We rated on a scale from 1 to 5 (with 1 being the least and 5 the best possible score). We have commented on our ratings as seen in Figure 1, so that everyone can follow the process and the reason why the specific ratings were given in each of those columns.

Project	Premise of the project in one simple phrase!	Accessibility	Discoverability	Publication	Reusability	Reproducibility	Transparency	Understandability	Collaboration	Evaluat
Human Brain Project	Sharing neural datasets for interdisciplinary research	5	4	5	5	Need to learn more on how to	5	4	4	Need to I
Event Horizon Telescope	Capturing images of black holes	5	3				5	5	4	3
Science Feedback	Ground truthing media, and science communication	5	5	Blog and FAQ but no real platform to discuss			5	5	5	5
Open Worm	OPEN source coding project to create a virtual organism	5	5				5	4	5	5
Safecast	Openly shared information on environmental radiation, based on volunteer data	5	5	not relevant	5	5	5	5	5	3
SenseBox	Toolkit for digital science for citizens to monitor environment	5	4	not relevant	5	5	4	5	3	5
Kiron	Online learning platform for refugees and disadvantaged communities	3.5	5	4.5	5	Articles published were cited and used by other	5	5	2.5	4

Figure 1: Screenshot of our Open Science Rating Project.

Results: Our result table can be found on our GitHub Open Science Repository(10). In conclusion, we have also commented on each of the given open science projects, the Positive remarks and the improvement remarks wherever necessary along with the total rating score as the final columns of our table(2).

Bibliography

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